

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ONIPEDE-OJO****FIRST NAME: OPEYEMI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 14%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following differentiates research-based writing from other persuasive writing?
 - Forces readers to accept a claim on the basics of authority.
 - Readers cannot follow the writer's reasoning from the evidence to the claim the writer draws from it.
 - It rests on shared facts that readers accept as truths independent of the writer's feelings and beliefs.¹**
 - It relies on blind trust.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Styles for Students and Researcher*, 9th ed. (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

2. What part of a dissertation has the potential to be the most satisfying, interesting, and meaningful aspect for the researcher?
- Methodology.
 - Discussion.**²
 - Introduction.
 - Conclusion.
3. Which of these countries failed to ratify the 1991 agreement on the European Economic Area of the EU extended to the countries of the EFTA?
- Switzerland.**³
 - Iceland.
 - Sweden.
 - Norway.
4. Which legal acts adopted under the treaties that form the European Union's second legislation are transposed into national legislation?
- Regulations.
 - Directives.**⁴
 - Decisions.

2. James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Florida: Florida State University Press, 2017), 56.

3. European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 77.

4. *Ibid.*, 79.

- All of the above.
5. The EU and its institutions are essentially funded from which of the following?
- Own resources.
- A proportion of each member state's harmonized VAT base.
- A resource based on Member States' gross national income.
- All of the above.**⁵
6. Which of the dissertation documents is sometimes referred to as the pre-prospectus?
- The Dissertation Prospectus.
- The Dissertation.
- The Dissertation Concept Paper.**⁶
- The Dissertation Manuscript.
7. When is a writer not guilty of plagiarism?
- When you quote or paraphrase someone else's words/work without credit.
- When the information used is common knowledge, fact, and available in numerous sources.**⁷
- When you copy and paste from the internet without giving credit to the owner of the work.

5. European Union, 94.

6. Sampson, 2.

7. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 37.

- Have someone write a paper for you and submit it as yours to your professor.
8. What issue in qualitative research does triangulation address?
- Objectivity.
- Transparency.
- Plausibility.
- Trustworthiness.**⁸
9. What is a footnote used for in a response paper at EUCLID
- To make reference to the source.
- To make reference to a page number.
- To clarify or comment.**⁹
- All of the above.
10. Which of the following is not true of a conceptual problem?
- The cost is always some tangible effect we do not like.**¹⁰
- The condition is always a version of not knowing or understanding something.
- It does not have a tangible cost or consequence.
- The consequence is a particular type of ignorance.

8. Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation; A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 145.

9. EUCLID University LMS, (ACA-401D Period 1 – EUCLID University LMS), min.7, sec.40, accessed November 15, 2023, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

10. Turabian, 29.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1*. Fourth. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

EUCLID University LMS. "ACA-401D Period 1 – EUCLID University LMS." Accessed November 15, 2023. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

European Union. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. European Commission, 2021.

Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Florida: Florida State University Press, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Styles for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.